

High cycle fatigue life estimation of punched and trimmed specimens considering residual stresses and surface roughness

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ABSTRACT

Shear cutting processes have a detrimental effect on fatigue of high strength metal components. The effect tends to increase with material grade, counteracting the task of reducing weight in chassis components using higher strength materials. Base material fatigue data are often available, but assessment of components with cut edges often require additional costly and time-consuming testing. This paper provides a methodology for estimation of fatigue life reduction by using residual stresses obtained from process simulations, and measured surface roughness in the cut edge. A stress relaxation criterion is applied to handle reduction of the initial local residual stresses. Two complex phase steels and one aluminum alloy are studied for validating the approach. Polished fatigue data is reduced to estimate $S-N$ curves of trimmed and punched specimens at different load ratios. Good agreement between the model and test results are found for all cases. The needed data for the predictions are only a high cycle $S-N$ relationship for polished material, uniaxial tensile properties, and the cut edge fracture surface residual stress and roughness without any parameter fitting, making it a convenient tool for estimating the reduction in fatigue life and for parameter studies.

1. Introduction

Shear cutting is a common process in the automotive and heavy duty vehicle (HDV) industry for creation of trim edges and holes. Knowledge about the resulting cut edge effect on fatigue of chassis components is crucial due to their exposure to cyclic loads [1,2]. Prediction of fatigue life reduction due to shear cutting processes is a complex task featuring multiple influencing factors with possible interactions. The tensile residual stresses in the cut edge could be regarded as tensile mean stresses and lowers the fatigue performance [3,4], and scatter in residual stresses in general heavily affects the fatigue life scatter [5]. In addition the geometrical defects such as larger notches and smaller notches, i.e. surface roughness, are important [6].

To the best of the authors knowledge, a fatigue life estimation method that is validated for different punched or trimmed sheet metals is lacking in the literature. The aim with the present paper is to address this gap by providing an approach that do not require residual stress measurements and extensive assumptions or parameter calibrations. Such an approach could, by extension to component level, be a valuable tool in chassis product development in the automotive and HDV industries, and could help to understand different parameter effects and interactions. Increased material strength could be used to decrease

weight, if the reduction in fatigue life due the increased process sensitivity is accounted for [1,2,7–10]. Today fatigue life predictions in this context are often based directly on fatigue data of polished specimens, potentially yielding non-conservative designs, or by applying safety factors to the same data, potentially yielding over-conservative and inefficient designs [11].

The fatigue life to crack initiation on component level was predicted in [9] using the Coffin-Manson relationship and the Morrow's mean stress correction. The studied material was S355MC with a tensile strength of 395 MPa. These strain life approaches require calibration of a set of strain-life parameters for each set of process parameters by conducting fatigue tests, and do not explicitly account for residual stresses and surface roughness.

A Murakami criterion was used in [6] to construct a Kitagawa diagram for prediction of the fatigue life of punched Fe-Si thin sheet specimens, considering that the crack propagation time was found to be negligible. Residual stresses were measured using X-ray diffraction techniques by stacking multiple thin sheets on top of each other to get sufficient sheet thickness for the measurement technique to be used. They found that the model prediction performance was heavily dependent on the different assumptions set by the user. The best

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prediction accuracy was found when local hardening was not accounted for, only the residual stresses, by treating them as static stresses. The residual stress used was an average of the measured values between the cut edge surface and a depth of 60 μm . A value related to the typical critical flaw size.

In [12] a non-local Crossland criterion [13] was used for strength assessment of punched, thin electrical steel sheets. To do this, 3D surface topography of punched specimens was performed. From this, critical defect geometries were identified and then transferred to a FE analysis for calculation of the stress field around the defects. One of the defect geometries was used for calibration of the critical distance limiting the volume over which the Crossland equivalent stress was averaged.

Experimentally measured surface roughness and compressive surface residual stresses were used in [14] to estimate fatigue life reduction of an abrasive water-jet cut high strength steel in the HCF (High Cycle Fatigue) regime above 10^4 cycles. This was done by applying two separate reduction factors. One to account for surface roughness and the other for residual stresses and nominal mean stress. Goodman mean stress correction was used and stress relaxation was not considered. The reduction factors were assumed to be independent of the number of cycles in the valid fatigue regime.

A Kitagawa diagram and Goodman mean stress correction were used in [10] to estimate the fatigue limit of trimmed steel specimens. They assumed that the residual stresses could be disregarded and that the threshold value for long crack propagation was equal for all steels.

The work presented in this article aims at providing a convenient approach for estimation of reduced high cycle fatigue life of high strength sheet metals in general, due to trimming and punching processes. This is done by reduction of polished fatigue life data for a load ratio of $R = -1$, considering residual stresses as any mean stresses, except for a simple stress relaxation criterion, and by applying reduction factors for surface roughness and notches. Exponents are added to the reduction factors to increase their impact as the number of cycles increases and surface related phenomena becomes more important for fatigue. As long as the $S-N$ curve for the base material is known, no additional fatigue tests are required. The residual stresses are obtained from punching simulations using a single parameter failure model that is calibrated against a punching experiment according to the simulation approach presented in [15]. This punching experiment could also provide the specimen needed for surface roughness measurements. Together with uniaxial tensile properties, i.e. yield stress and tensile strength, these are the only required data. No further assumptions or parameter calibrations are needed.

2. Theory

2.1. Shear cutting and fatigue

One important shear cutting process parameter, concerning fatigue, is the cutting clearance [8,16–18]. This parameter is defined as the gap between the punch and the die, expressed as a percentage of the sheet thickness, see Fig. 1(a) [15]. A rule of thumb is that fatigue performance decreases with increased cutting clearance. This is not always true as shown in [8] where one explanation was that the surface roughness decreased for increased cutting clearance. The metal sheet cut edge, resulting from the process, could be divided into the zones shown in Fig. 1(b) [15,19]. The most critical zone for fatigue is often the fracture zone [20,21] where both the surface roughness [6,22], and the (tangential) tensile residual stresses [3,23,24], usually are higher than in the other zones. Several works [11,15,25] also shows that the hardness is higher in the fracture zone than in the burr zone. This might affect the crack initiation, especially in the LCF (Low Cycle Fatigue) regime, as discussed in [26] where the increased hardness is claimed to restrict dislocation slip. In HCF the negative effect of increased surface roughness and tensile residual stresses seems

Fig. 1. Schematic sketches of (a) shear cutting process setup; (b) cut edge zones. From [15], used under Creative Commons CC-BY license.

to be more important than the increased hardness in the fracture zone considering the findings in [6,20,27] where it is shown that the fatigue crack initiate in this zone despite the assumed increased hardness. In some cases the burr of the cut edge could, depending on the shape, provide an additional geometric stress concentration detrimental to the fatigue performance [2,6].

2.2. Stress-life modeling

The stress amplitude σ_a in the HCF regime can be described by the Basquin relationship [28]

$$\sigma_a = C N^{-1/m} \quad (1)$$

where C and m are calibration parameters, and N is the number of cycles to failure. In this work, C and m are calibrated to the high cycle fatigue test results for specimens with polished edges, presented in Tables A.6 and A.7 using the least squares method. The aluminum parameters are obtained from [29] where the yield stress and tensile strength deviates 2.7% and 1.2%, respectively, from the values presented in Table 1. Hence, it was assumed that the different material batches exhibit similar fatigue performance. The Basquin parameters were obtained using specimens with an elastic stress concentration factor of 1.15 and 1.05, see Table 3. This was not accounted since the compressive residual stresses and fine surface in the polished edges is assumed to counteract the stress concentration.

2.3. Mean stress effect on fatigue

If a nominal stress amplitude at a given number of cycles σ_{aR} is known at a stress ratio $R = \sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max}$ other than $R = -1$, the $R = -1$ equivalent σ_{a-1} can be estimated using the Gerber parabola mean stress correction factor defined by [30,31]

$$\sigma_{a-1} = \frac{1}{1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_{mR}}{\sigma_{uts}}\right)^2} \sigma_{aR}, \quad (2)$$

where σ_{mR} is the nominal mean stress. Other common expressions for mean stress correction are Goodman, Morrow, Smith Watson Topper (SWT), and Walker [32]. Along with the Gerber expression, Goodman and SWT does not require any additional material parameters. Gerber correction was used in [29], from where the Basquin parameters used for aluminum in this paper were obtained. In [33], Gerber correction was found to give better agreement with experiments as compared to the Goodman relationship for a wide range of high strength steels. In addition to the mentioned methods above, the FKM-guideline [34,35] provides an approach where different mean stress correction factors are used for different ranges of load ratio and types of materials.

2.4. Effect of surface roughness on fatigue

A common approach to account for surface roughness in fatigue life predictions is to use a reduction factor K_r on the $R = -1$ fatigue

Fig. 2. Stress relaxation model [39].

data of the base/polished material. This factor is empirical and various expressions are proposed in the literature [14,34]. The expression used in this work is the one used in the FKM-guideline, which for normal stresses reads [34,35]

$$K_r = 1 - a_R \log_{10}(R_z) \log_{10} \left(\frac{2\sigma_{uts}}{\sigma_{uts,min}} \right), \quad (3)$$

where R_z is the mean peak to valley height of the roughness profile in μm according to standard [36], a_R and $\sigma_{uts,min}$ are material and process specific parameters. For steels and wrought aluminum alloys $a_R = 0.22$ [34,35]. $\sigma_{uts,min}$ is 400 MPa and 133 MPa for steels and aluminum alloys, respectively [34,35]. For steels, the expression for K_r , suggested in [14] using the arithmetic mean roughness R_a provides similar results.

2.5. Effect of residual stresses and stress relaxation on fatigue

Residual stresses, and especially residual stress relaxation effect on fatigue, is a complex task but some conclusions can be drawn from the literature. Hayama et al. [37] studied three different high strength steels featuring compressive surface residual stresses, and found that the relaxation threshold, the stress level where cyclic relaxation began to be noticeable, correlated linearly to the yield strength of the material. Leguinagoicoa et al. [38] found that for lower cyclic stresses the residual stresses stabilize at a certain level. The residual stress level effect on the fatigue limit was estimated through modeling in [4]. In that estimation model the fatigue limit decreases with increased tensile residual stress up to a certain value where the fatigue limit remains constant even though the residual stresses increase.

A simple model to estimate the stabilized residual stress, supported by experimental evidence, was indicated in [39], see Fig. 2. This model is consistent with the mentioned findings above in the sense that the relaxation threshold is directly linked to the monotonic yield stress and that the relaxed stress level is independent of the number of cycles in the high cycle fatigue regime where the cyclic stresses are relatively low. Above a certain level of initial residual stress, the fatigue strength is unaffected by a further increase of residual stress.

2.6. Notch effect on fatigue

Geometrical notches and their effects on fatigue has been extensively studied for several years [40], see for example [41,42]. Normally the fatigue notch sensitivity increases with material grade [43]. For a fully notch sensitive material the elastic stress concentration factor K_t equals the fatigue notch factor K_f at the fatigue limit [41,42]. Full notch sensitivity is assumed in this work. Compared to calculations using the Peterson or the Neuber size parameters presented in [42] for a material with similar tensile strength as the steels studied in this work, the assumption of full sensitivity yields an error of around 2% or 10%, respectively, for the specimen with the punched hole in Fig. 3.

Table 1

Yield stress σ_y at 0.2% plastic strain, tensile strength σ_{uts} and elongation of the studied materials. Tested in the transverse to rolling direction [15].

Mtrl.	σ_y [MPa]	σ_{uts} [MPa]	Uniform Elong. [%]	Tot. Elong. [%]	Nr. of specimens
HR CP800SF	778	835	6.7	16.5 (A50)	3
HR CP980SF	957	1034	4.9	12.8 (A50)	3
AA6082-T6	298	333	8.3	12.9 (A80)	5

3. Material and methods

3.1. Materials

Three different high strength metals were investigated. Two hot rolled complex phase steels of grade 800 and 980, with sheet thicknesses 3.4 mm and 3.5 mm, respectively, as well as one aluminum alloy, AA6082-T6, with sheet thickness 2.0 mm. The uniaxial tensile mechanical properties in the transverse to rolling direction of the investigated materials are presented in Table 1 and their chemical composition in Table 2. This direction corresponds to the loading direction in the fatigue experiments.

3.2. Manufacturing of shear cut specimens

For each material presented in Table 1, two types of shear cut specimens were produced in a servo-hydraulic machine, see Fig. 3. Those were trimmed (open cut) and punched (closed cut), with the elastic stress concentration factors $K_t = 1.03$ [44] and $K_t = 2.24$, respectively. The stress concentration factor for punched specimens was obtained using [45]

$$K_t = 2 + 0.284 \left(1 - \frac{d}{H}\right) - 0.600 \left(1 - \frac{d}{H}\right)^2 + 1.32 \left(1 - \frac{d}{H}\right)^3, \quad (4)$$

where H is the total specimen width and d is the hole diameter. HR CP800SF were produced using 8.8% cutting clearance, HR CP980SF using 8.6% and 17%, and AA6082-T6 using 7.5%. The shear cutting procedure is described in detail in [15].

3.3. Fatigue testing of polished and shear cut specimens

Uniaxial fatigue testing of the polished, flat steel specimens was performed according to standard [46] to obtain the base material data. The flat surfaces were left in as-rolled condition. The load ratio R was -1 and K_f was 1.05, the cycle shape sinusoidal and the frequency between 25 and 28 Hz. To obtain the endurance limit of the polished condition staircase testing based on the Dixon-Mood method [47] was utilized. It is important to note that finding the fatigue limit of polished specimens is not necessary for the reduction approach described below, it was merely used for comparison. Fatigue testing of polished AA6082-T6 was not conducted. Instead, fatigue data from literature was relied upon and the Basquin relationship proposed in [29] was used. The shear cut specimens were tested using sinusoidal, uniaxial loading and frequencies between 10 Hz and 40 Hz. Total fracture was used as failure criteria in all fatigue tests. The test setups for the punched and trimmed specimens are shown in Fig. 4.

3.4. Surface roughness measurements

The edges of the cut specimens were analyzed using a 3D profilometer, specifically the Alicona InfiniteFocusSL equipped with a 10x lens. The trimmed specimens were directly placed in the profilometer and examined in the central part of the specimen where the cross-section was the minimum. Similarly, the punched specimens were cut in the longitudinal direction and then positioned in the profilometer to capture the surface profile of the cut edge. Roughness values were measured in both the burnish and fracture zones using the SensoMap topography analysis software on the obtained surface roughness images.

Table 2
Chemical composition of the studied materials (wt.%). Maximum content presented for the steels [15].

Mtrl.	Fe	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Al	Cu	B	Ti+Nb	Cr+Mo	–
HR CP800SF	Bal.	0.18	1.0	2.2	0.05	0.01	1.2	0.2	0.01	0.25	1.0	–
HR CP980SF	Bal.	0.20	1.0	2.2	0.05	0.01	1.2	0.2	0.01	0.25	1.0	–
Mtrl.	Fe	Mg	Si	Mn	Pb	Zn	Al	Cu	Ca	Cd	Ti	Cr
AA6082-T6	0.37	0.85	0.97	0.54	0.00	0.02	97.1	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.01

Fig. 3. Geometries of trimmed ($K_t = 1.03$) [44] and punched ($K_t = 2.24$) specimens.

Fig. 4. Fatigue test setup for (a) Trimmed specimens; (b) Punched specimens.

3.5. Modeling of the shear cutting process to obtain residual stresses

The surface residual stresses in the loading direction were obtained from FEM (Finite Element Method) simulations of the shear cutting process, described in detail in [15] using one punching experiment and one uniaxial tensile test per material for calibration of the failure model and the flow curve, respectively. It was assumed that the surface residual stresses in the loading direction was equal for both trimming and punching, given the same cutting clearance. This assumption was controlled by simulating the trimming process of HR CP980SF using cutting clearance 8.6%. Residual stresses obtained from punching simulations of HR CP980SF were validated in [15] using focused ion beam-digital image correlation (FIB-DIC). The values presented in Table 5 and used in the proposed fatigue life estimation approach was the average of the 30 mostly stressed elements in the fracture zone of the cut edge, see Figs. 5 and 6, corresponding to an area of 0.012 mm^2 . These figures also show that the elements used for the residual stress calculation are all located within 3–4 element lengths from the cut edge surface. This equals a distance of around 60–80 μm , which could be compared to the value of 60 μm used in [6].

4. Reduced fatigue life estimation procedure

This section presents the proposed approach to estimate the reduced stress amplitude σ'_a as a function of the number of cycles N at a specific load ratio R for punched and trimmed specimens. The required data are:

- A relationship between the cycles to failure and stress amplitude for specimens with polished edges.
- The uniaxial ultimate tensile strength σ_{uts} and the monotonic yield stress σ_y for the material.
- The surface roughness R_z .
- The surface residual stresses in the loading direction after the cutting process σ_{res}^0 .

The surface roughness and residual stresses of interest are those obtained in the fracture zone of the cut edge as this is the expected initiation region of the fatigue crack as described earlier.

The approach is based on four assumptions:

- The local maximum stress in a polished specimen at a specific load ratio is described by the sum of the maximum nominal stress

Fig. 5. Residual stress field in fatigue loading direction (Z) for the investigated steels. (a) HR CP800SF, cutting clearance 8.8%; (b) HR CP980SF cutting, clearance 8.6%; (c) HR CP980SF, cutting clearance 17%.

Fig. 6. Residual stress field in fatigue loading direction (Z) for the investigated aluminum alloy using 7.5% cutting clearance.

at that load ratio and the residual normal stress in the loading direction.

- The local maximum stress after cyclic relaxation can never exceed the monotonic yield stress.
- No cyclic stress relaxation occurs if the maximum local stress is below the yield stress.
- The stress relaxation is independent of the number of cycles in the HCF regime since the relaxation has occurred before this regime.

With these assumptions, and having the quantities described above determined, the reduced stress amplitude can be estimated by

$$\sigma'_a = K_{m\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{K_t} \right)^{h_t} K_r^{h_r} \sigma_{a-1} \quad (5)$$

where σ_{a-1} is the $S-N$ curve relationship for polished edge specimens at $R = -1$ and $K_t = 1$, K_t is the elastic stress concentration factor, and K_r is the surface roughness related fatigue reduction factor proposed in the FKM-guideline [34,35], presented in Eq. (3).

To account for the residual stresses a reduction factor $K_{m\sigma}$ is proposed, based on Eq. (2), so that

$$K_{m\sigma} = 1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_{mR} + \sigma_{res}}{\sigma_{uts}} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

where σ_{res} are the estimated residual stresses after cyclic stress relaxation. The only difference as compared to the Gerber parabola expression is that σ_{res} is superimposed on the nominal mean stress of

Table 3

Basquin parameters for the studied materials in polished condition at $R = -1$. Source: The values for AA6082-T6 are obtained from [29].

Material	C	m	K_t
HR CP800SF	2004.80	7.885	1.05
HR CP980SF	1536.35	9.749	1.05
AA6082-T6	581.47	8.333	1.15

the polished specimens at the load ratio of interest. The stress relaxation criterion [39] is applied according to Fig. 2, so that

$$\sigma_{res} = \begin{cases} \sigma_y - \sigma_{max}, & \text{if } \sigma_{res}^0 > \sigma_y - \sigma_{max} \\ \sigma_{res}^0, & \text{if } \sigma_{res}^0 \leq \sigma_y - \sigma_{max} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where σ_{max} is the maximum nominal stress for polished specimens at the stress ratio R to be predicted, calculated by

$$\sigma_{max} = \sigma_{mR} + \sigma_{aR} = \sigma_{mR} \left[1 + \left(\frac{1-R}{1+R} \right) \right]. \quad (8)$$

Since σ_{mR} and σ_{aR} are obtained before application of the factors K_r and K_t the local stress increase due to notches and surface roughness is implicitly accounted for in the stress relaxation calculation.

From the Gerber parabola expression in Eq. (2) also follows that if the nominal mean stress $\sigma_{mR} \neq 0$, then σ_{mR} can be calculated by

$$\sigma_{mR} = \frac{\sigma_{uts} \sqrt{4 \left(\frac{1+R}{1-R} \right)^2 \sigma_{a-1}^2 + \sigma_{uts}^2 - \sigma_{uts}^2}}{2 \left(\frac{1+R}{1-R} \right) \sigma_{a-1}}. \quad (9)$$

The exponents h_t and h_r in Eq. (5) are added to increase the impact of both the surface roughness and the elastic stress concentration factor from 0 in the LCF regime, where the fatigue mechanisms are governed more by global plasticity within the specimen [6], to 1 at $N = 10^6$. The reason for h_t and h_r to reach a value of 1 at one million cycles is purely empirical and based on the fact that the correction factors traditionally have been established for this number of cycles [34]. The point where these functions obtain a value of zero, i.e. where no impact is assumed, differs depending on which mechanism the reduction factor accounts for. For notches this intersection point can be set to $N = 10^0$ [34], which is used for h_t in this work. For the surface roughness related factor h_r , a value of $N = 10^3$ could be used [48,49]. Here it is proposed to use $N = 10^4$ instead, which is supported by some experimental evidence, depending on material grade [49]. This leads to

$$h_t = \frac{1}{6} \log_{10}(N) \quad (10)$$

and

$$h_r = \frac{1}{2} \log_{10} \left(\frac{N}{10^4} \right). \quad (11)$$

Fig. 7. Estimation of reduced 50% failure probability HR CP800SF $S-N$ curve $\sigma'_a(N)$ in the HCF regime for (a) Trimmed specimens, $R = -1$; (b) Trimmed specimens, $R = 0.1$; (c) Punched specimens, $R = 0.1$. Filled markers for failures (fail.), and white markers for runouts (RO). The solid line is the 50% failure probability $S-N$ curve of the polished edge specimens at $R = -1$.

Fig. 8. Estimation of reduced 50% failure probability HR CP980SF $S-N$ curve $\sigma'_a(N)$ in the HCF regime for (a) Trimmed specimens, $R = -1$, cutting clearances 8.6% and 17%; (b) Trimmed specimens, $R = 0.1$; (c) Punched specimens, $R = 0.1$, cutting clearances 8.6% and 17%. Filled markers for failures (fail.), and white markers for runouts (RO). The solid line is the 50% failure probability $S-N$ curve of the polished edge specimens at $R = -1$.

Fig. 9. Estimation of reduced 50% failure probability AA6082-T6 $S-N$ curve $\sigma'_a(N)$ in the HCF regime for (a) Trimmed specimens, $R = -1$; (b) Trimmed specimens, $R = 0.1$; (c) Punched specimens, $R = 0.1$. Filled markers for failures (fail.), and white markers for runouts (RO). The dash-dotted line is the reference curve [29].

Fig. 10. Accuracy of the model in estimating the reduced fatigue lives of punched (P) and trimmed (T) specimens at $R = -1$ and $R = 0.1$, made of (a) HR CP800SF using cutting clearance 8.8%; (b) HR CP980SF using cutting clearance 8.6% and 17%; (c) AA6082-T6 using cutting clearance 7.5%.

Table 4

Mean peak to valley height of roughness profile R_z and arithmetic mean roughness R_a in the fracture (Frac.) and burnish (Burn.) zones, and R_z of the as rolled surface. (T) denotes trimmed and (P) denotes punched specimens. CCL denotes cutting clearance.

Material	CCL [%]	R_z Frac. [μm]	R_z Burn. [μm]	R_a Frac. [μm]	R_a Burn. [μm]	R_z As-rolled [μm]
HR CP800SF (P)	8.8	21.3	4.1	5.0	2.3	3.1
HR CP800SF (T)	8.8	19.1	7.9	3.1	1.1	3.1
HR CP980SF (P)	8.6	10.1	6.5	2.7	2.5	^a
HR CP980SF (P)	17	6.2	6.0	2.2	2.4	^a
AA6082-T6 (T)	7.5	22.9	13.5	4.0	2.1	1.0

^a Equal values as for HR CP800SF are assumed.

Limits were set to the exponents so that the value could not be less than 0 or exceed 1.

The presented approach provides a possibility to, without any fitting parameters other than the ones used for the base material $S-N$ curve, estimate the fatigue life of punched and trimmed specimens. The surface roughness reduction factor is calculated directly from the surface roughness R_z , the elastic fatigue notch factor is assumed to equal the elastic stress concentration factor, and the increasing effect of these factors as the number of cycles increase, is accounted for by the use of cycle dependent exponents. The residual stresses are treated as any mean stress through the Gerber mean stress correction expression, except for a simple relaxation criteria that is based on the yield stress. The approach is validated for high cycle fatigue above approximately 10^4 cycles.

5. Results

5.1. Fatigue testing of polished and shear cut specimens

The fatigue test results for polished and shear cut specimens are presented in Tables A.6–A.8. The fitted Basquin parameters for polished specimens are presented in Table 3. The parameters for AA6082-T6 are obtained from [29].

5.2. Surface roughness measurements

The surface roughness measurements for the shear cut specimens are presented in Table 4. It can be observed that the measurement values are in the same range as the values obtained in [2,11] for punched S500MC and trimmed DP800, respectively. Table 4 shows that not all the tested configurations were evaluated for surface roughness. For the missing configurations it was assumed that the surface roughness in fracture zone of a trimmed and punched specimen were equal given the same material and cutting clearance. This assumption was validated by comparing the fracture zone R_z values which was 21.3 and 19.1 μm for punched and trimmed specimens, respectively. This yields a difference in K_r of less than 1%. Hence, it was concluded that the missing values could be taken from the corresponding trimmed or punched specimen.

The arithmetic mean surface roughness of the polished edges was $R_a \leq 0.2 \mu\text{m}$. The as-rolled surface was kept for all specimens and the roughness of as-rolled HR CP980SF and HR CP800SF was assumed to be equal.

5.3. Residual stresses

The initial residual stresses used for validation of the approach are presented in Table 5. These values are obtained from FEM simulations of the punching process and are the average of the 30 most severely stressed (in the loading direction) elements in the fracture zone, corresponding to an area of approximately 0.012 mm^2 using element size 0.02 mm. Simulation of trimming of HR CP980SF using cutting clearance 8.6% yields an initial residual stress value that deviates around 5% from the punching counterpart, indicating that only considering the residual stresses from punching is a defensible simplification.

Table 5

Initial tensile residual stress σ_{res}^0 from simulations of the cutting process for each studied material and cutting clearance.

Material	Cutting clearance [%]	Initial residual stress [MPa]
HR CP800SF	8.8	604
HR CP980SF	8.6	672
HR CP980SF	17	909
AA6082-T6	7.5	53

Fig. 11. Surface appearance of punched HR CP980SF using cutting clearances (a) 8.6%; (b) 17%.

5.4. Fatigue performance: Test and predictions

The polished specimen test results and corresponding $S-N$ curves are shown in Figs. 7–9, which also features the estimations of the reduced $S-N$ curves according to the proposed approach (dashed lines) and the fatigue tests of shear cut specimens for validation.

The accuracy of the approach to estimate fatigue life is presented in Fig. 10. Two experiments, of 106 in total, lies outside an error factor of three. One on the non-conservative side.

6. Discussion

Fig. 8(c) shows that the model predicts almost the same fatigue life for punched HR CP980SF specimens using 8.6% and 17% cutting clearance, while all experiments using 17% failed earlier than their 8.6% counterparts. This discrepancy could have multiple sources. One could be that nominal stresses are used. Due to the process setup, all cutting clearances will, in principle, result in the same hole diameter at the top of the sheet, while the hole diameter at the bottom, facing towards the die, will increase with the cutting clearance. Hence, cutting clearance 17% might result in slightly higher stresses due to the smaller cross section. An effect that should be negligible at component level, but increase as the specimen size decrease. Another source might be the surface roughness measurement position. As seen in Fig. 11(b) there exist a seemingly rough transition zone between the burnish and the fracture zone using 17% cutting clearance, which is not observed for 8.6%. For both clearances the roughness was measured further down in the fracture zone. Thirdly, the residual stress relaxation criterion

Fig. 12. HR CP980SF fatigue fracture surfaces of (a) Trimmed specimen, cutting clearance 8.6%, $R = -1$, 249 MPa; (b) Trimmed specimen, cutting clearance 8.6%, $R = -1$, 410 MPa; (c) Trimmed specimen, cutting clearance 17%, $R = -1$, 240 MPa; (d) Trimmed specimen, cutting clearance 8.6%, $R = 0.1$, 306 MPa; (e) Trimmed specimen, cutting clearance 8.6%, $R = 0.1$, 194 MPa; (f) Punched specimen, cutting clearance 17%, $R = -1$, 109 MPa.

Fig. 13. Trimmed HR CP980SF secondary cracks (a) Cutting clearance 8.6%, $R = -1$, 410 MPa; (b) Cutting clearance 17%, $R = -1$, 240 MPa.

might have an effect. In this case the relaxation criterion eliminates the difference in initial residual stresses shown in Table 5 by reducing them to $\sigma_y - \sigma_{max}$ according to Eq. (7).

The fatigue fracture surfaces presented in Fig. 12 reveals that it is difficult to give a definite answer regarding the exact crack initiation location. Hence, it could not be confirmed that the rough transition zone in Fig. 11(b) has an impact. Attempts to localize initiation points by ocular inspection are marked with squares. The crack seems to initiate in the fracture zone of the cut edge regardless of load level, material and specimen geometry. However, it should be noted that the tests in this work reach a number of cycles of around thirty thousand cycles and above which is well within the HCF regime. In the LCF regime the crack initiation location might change due to a decreased importance of the surface condition [20].

At some trimmed specimens of CP980 tested at $R = -1$ secondary cracks were observed. Two examples indicating a possible difference between cutting clearance 8.6% and 17% are presented in Fig. 13 where the cracks seems to initiate closer to the burnish zone using 17%. It should be noted that the tests were performed at different load levels.

The reason for two of the experiments in Fig. 10 to be outside an error factor of three could be found in the $S-N$ curves in Figs. 8(b) and 9(c), where it seems like these experiments are located in the region where a transition from surface to sub-surface initiated cracks could be expected. The specimens featuring a surface initiation would then have significantly lower fatigue life than the specimens with sub-surface initiation, and hence the scatter in this region could be significant [50,51].

Many of the shear cut experiments reaching one million cycles were considered as run outs. This run out condition is not ideal in view of that many failures occurred close to one million cycles. This means that some information about failures that likely would have occurred slightly above one million cycles is lost. This also makes the validity of the reduced curve in this cycle range questionable. Aluminum it

is generally considered to exhibit a lack of a knee or fatigue limit in the $S-N$ curve and hence it could be speculated that good agreement is found also above one million cycles. Steels on the other hand, often features an endurance limit in the HCF regime. The number of cycles of this expected plateau cannot be predicted using this method. However, using the Basquin relationship as a base for the calculations, not considering the fatigue limit of the polished edge specimens, should give a more conservative estimate of the $S-N$ curve.

The base material $S-N$ curve for AA6082-T6 was, as mentioned, obtained from the literature [29] where a different specimen geometry, a different material batch and a different sheet thickness was used. The fatigue tests were performed at $R = 0.1$ and the Basquin parameters for $R = -1$ were obtained using Gerber mean stress correction. The surface condition of the specimens are also unclear. Hence the results concerning the aluminum alloy should be handled with more care than the results for the steels.

The stress relaxation criterion, although simple, is a key ingredient in all validation examples presented in Figs. 7–9, while it is less crucial for AA6082-T6 which seems to be less sensitive to residual stresses as shown below. Without the relaxation criterion only two of all the experiments using steel specimens would be within an error factor of three. It is important to note that the stress relaxation model was originally developed for welded joints and measurements of the residual stress relaxation in shear cut edges has not been performed in this work. To strengthen the foundation of this approach such measurements are desirable.

Improvements in prediction accuracy could most likely be achieved by a more accurate description of the cyclic behavior and the work hardening of the materials resulting from the cutting process, which might affect the stress relaxation and the crack initiation. This would, however, come at a prize of significantly added complexity.

The staircase testing utilized in this work did not fulfill the validity conditions for estimation of the standard deviation. Hence, the accuracy of this estimation is unclear. Generally more accurate results could be achieved using stress levels equally spaced in the logarithmic space, following the methodology described in [52].

The as-rolled surface of the polished edge specimens in this work was assumed to be perfect. Table 4 reveals the true roughness. A roughness of $3.1 \mu\text{m}$ yields a difference in K_r of around 7% as compared to $1 \mu\text{m}$ for HR CP800SF. To only consider this without considering possible compressive residual stresses on the as-rolled surface [53] could decrease the prediction performance since the residual stresses and the surface roughness would have counteracting effects. A more detailed characterization of the as rolled surface could provide further insights and a more correctly described base material $S-N$ curve.

In Figs. 14 and 15 the effect of surface roughness and residual stresses are separated for the different materials. Assuming that the model is valid for describing the effects separately, a difference can be observed between the steels and the aluminum alloy. For the latter

Fig. 14. Effect of neglecting initial residual stresses and surface roughness reduction in fatigue life estimation of shear cut specimens, assuming $R = -1$ and $K_t = 1.03$. Trimming of (a) HR CP800SF using cutting clearance 8.8%; (b) HR CP980SF using cutting clearance 8.6%; (c) AA6082-T6 using cutting clearance 7.5%.

Fig. 15. Effect of neglecting initial residual stresses and surface roughness reduction in fatigue life estimation of shear cut specimens, assuming $R = 0.1$ and $K_t = 2.24$. Punching of (a) HR CP800SF using cutting clearance 8.8%; (b) HR CP980SF using cutting clearance 8.6%; (c) AA6082-T6 using cutting clearance 7.5%.

the model implies that surface roughness accounts for the major part of the fatigue life reduction at $R = -1$. For the steels the opposite applies. For punched specimens tested at $R = 0.1$ the increase in fatigue life by removing initial stresses or improving the surface seems to be much less pronounced, being almost negligible below 10^5 cycles. The reason for this seems to be that the nominal maximum stresses are higher and hence the stress relaxation are more exaggerated.

In general, higher maximum stresses are expected for $S-N$ curves at $R = 0.1$ as compared to $R = -1$ for a given number of cycles. This means that if high tensile residual stresses are present the model will yield more stress relaxation for $R = 0.1$ than for $R = -1$, which leads to a less pronounced effect of those residual stresses.

The approach presented above is not validated for cut edges featuring significant burr formation as this could not be found in the specimens examined in this work, neither in simulations, see Figs. 5 and 6, nor experimentally, see Fig. 16. Significant burr formation is usually obtained for higher cutting clearances.

In this work the mean stress and residual stress reduction factor $K_{m\sigma}$ is formulated based on the Gerber mean stress correction factor as described earlier. In the aluminum case the experiments that are behind the Basquin relationship were made for $R = 0.1$ and then increased using the Gerber relationship to form the base material expression at $R = -1$. Hence, it was natural to use Gerber also in the reduction phase even though the real mean stress dependency was not evaluated. It is well known that different materials exhibit different mean stress dependencies [54]. Knowing this it could be possible to further increase the prediction performance by utilization of for example the FKM-guideline for mean stress correction which handles differences in material type and differences in load ratio. However, this require the use of different expressions for different regimes of R . For simplicity this approach was not used in this work. For the same reason the

Fig. 16. Edge profiles of (a) Trimmed HR CP800SF using cutting clearance 8.8%; (b) Punched HR CP980SF using cutting clearance 8.6%; (c) Trimmed AA6082-T6 using cutting clearance 7.5%.

elastic stress concentration was used instead of a more complex way of handling the increased notch root stresses. Both these factors thus exhibit possibilities for improved prediction accuracy if the cost of increased complexity is manageable. If the mean stress correction factor is changed, then Eqs. (6) and (9) have to be adjusted accordingly.

The steels studied in this work are both hot rolled high strength complex phase steels of comparable thicknesses. These are grades of high interest for light-weighting of chassis components in the HDV industry where punching and trimming are commonly used processes.

Utilization of the methodology on a widely different steel could require adjustments of mainly the mean stress correction factor and the stress concentration factor. A lower strength steel is for example expected to be less notch sensitive.

7. Conclusions

An approach to estimate the high cycle fatigue life of trimmed and punched specimens of high strength metals at different nominal stress ratios is proposed in this paper. The only required data are the surface roughness in the fracture zone of the cut edge, the surface residual stresses in the same area, obtained either from simulations, as presented in this work, or from measurements. In addition, a fatigue model for specimens with polished edges in the HCF regime, and standard uniaxial tensile test data, such as the yield stress and ultimate tensile strength, must be available. The main conclusions from this study are:

- i. Knowing uniaxial tensile properties, base material fatigue performance, surface roughness and residual stresses in the fracture zone of the cut edge, could be enough to accurately, below an error factor of three, estimate the reduced fatigue life in the HCF regime.
- ii. Assuming that the approach is valid for describing the effects of roughness and residual stresses separately, the residual stresses accounts for a larger part of the fatigue performance reduction for the steels. For AA6082-T6 the opposite applies, the effect of residual stresses from the cutting process is almost negligible. This suggests that for example heat treatments to reduce the residual stresses would be more effective for steels, especially for the higher grade HR CP980SF. It also suggests that for AA6082-T6 the main focus in improving fatigue performance of shear cut sheets should be on lowering the surface roughness.
- iii. Accounting for cyclic stress relaxation is crucial for the reduced fatigue life estimation accuracy.
- iv. According to the model the effect of residual stresses is more pronounced in fatigue testing at load ratio $R = -1$ as compared to $R = 0.1$.

Table A.6

HR CP800SF fatigue test results, rounded to the nearest ten, of polished (transverse direction), trimmed (T) and punched (P) specimens. Cutting clearances as percentage of sheet thickness.

Edge cond.	Load ratio	σ_a [MPa]	N [cycles]	Edge cond.	Load ratio	σ_a [MPa]	N [cycles]
Polished	-1	520	50 580	T 8.8%	-1	256	288 050
Polished	-1	520	31 810	T 8.8%	-1	256	320 760
Polished	-1	480	112 770	T 8.8%	-1	256	345 450
Polished	-1	480	90 510	T 8.8%	-1	216	498 770
Polished	-1	480	97 020	T 8.8%	-1	216	643 230
Polished	-1	440	133 600	T 8.8%	-1	175	>2 022 480
Polished	-1	440	122 970	T 8.8%	0.1	309	80 960
Polished	-1	420	189 620	T 8.8%	0.1	309	89 760
Polished	-1	420	183 750	T 8.8%	0.1	309	71 180
Polished	-1	420	333 260	T 8.8%	0.1	265	266 530
Polished	-1	400	>2 000 000	T 8.8%	0.1	265	236 110
Polished	-1	400	455 880	T 8.8%	0.1	265	204 240
Polished	-1	400	445 010	T 8.8%	0.1	221	532 980
Polished	-1	400	143 910	T 8.8%	0.1	221	533 670
Polished	-1	380	>2 000 000	T 8.8%	0.1	221	594 440
Polished	-1	380	616 100	T 8.8%	0.1	221	>1 000 000
Polished	-1	380	653 830	T 8.8%	0.1	199	664 320
Polished	-1	360	>2 000 000	T 8.8%	0.1	199	>1 000 000
Polished	-1	360	>2 000 000	P 8.8%	0.1	156	76 190
Polished	-1	360	>2 000 000	P 8.8%	0.1	156	101 310
T 8.8%	-1	422	34 140	P 8.8%	0.1	156	101 030
T 8.8%	-1	422	40 740	P 8.8%	0.1	111	352 850
T 8.8%	-1	422	51 990	P 8.8%	0.1	111	295 620
T 8.8%	-1	367	92 820	P 8.8%	0.1	111	232 870
T 8.8%	-1	367	85 760	P 8.8%	0.1	100	207 070
T 8.8%	-1	367	103 230	P 8.8%	0.1	100	442 960
T 8.8%	-1	312	106 890	P 8.8%	0.1	72	904 960
T 8.8%	-1	312	158 870	P 8.8%	0.1	72	>1 080 060
T 8.8%	-1	312	125 810				

CRedit authorship contribution statement

David Gustafsson: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Sergi Parareda:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Rémi Munier:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Erik Olsson:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix. Fatigue test results

See [Tables A.6–A.8](#).

Table A.7

HR CP980SF fatigue test results, rounded to the nearest ten, of polished (transverse direction), trimmed (T) and punched (P) specimens. Cutting clearances as percentage of sheet thickness.

Edge cond.	Load ratio	σ_a [MPa]	N [cycles]	Edge cond.	Load ratio	σ_a [MPa]	N [cycles]
Polished	-1	480	145 150	T 17%	-1	200	>1 485 980
Polished	-1	480	51 110	T 8.6%	0.1	306	68 860
Polished	-1	420	457 460	T 8.6%	0.1	306	90 740
Polished	-1	420	280 550	T 8.6%	0.1	306	106 750
Polished	-1	420	197 600	T 8.6%	0.1	269	169 360
Polished	-1	400	>2 000 000	T 8.6%	0.1	269	147 670
Polished	-1	400	>2 000 000	T 8.6%	0.1	269	129 190
Polished	-1	400	896 650	T 8.6%	0.1	231	234 260
Polished	-1	400	612 290	T 8.6%	0.1	231	184 260
Polished	-1	400	433 430	T 8.6%	0.1	231	294 540
Polished	-1	400	292 250	T 8.6%	0.1	194	560 530
Polished	-1	380	>2 000 000	T 8.6%	0.1	194	610 720
Polished	-1	380	>2 000 000	T 8.6%	0.1	194	520 790
Polished	-1	380	>2 000 000	T 8.6%	0.1	194	469 380
T 8.6%	-1	410	47 500	T 8.6%	0.1	185	352 240
T 8.6%	-1	410	49 170	T 8.6%	0.1	185	>1 000 000
T 8.6%	-1	410	60 500	T 8.6%	0.1	185	>1 000 000
T 8.6%	-1	357	88 960	T 8.6%	0.1	185	>1 000 000
T 8.6%	-1	357	74 810	T 8.6%	0.1	185	>1 000 000
T 8.6%	-1	357	60 940	T 8.6%	0.1	177	>1 000 000
T 8.6%	-1	303	132 470	P 8.6%	0.1	144	116 670
T 8.6%	-1	303	111 300	P 8.6%	0.1	144	104 480
T 8.6%	-1	303	123 760	P 8.6%	0.1	109	460 250
T 8.6%	-1	249	234 640	P 8.6%	0.1	109	474 730
T 8.6%	-1	249	327 350	P 8.6%	0.1	109	278 830
T 8.6%	-1	249	256 110	P 8.6%	0.1	91	>1 000 000
T 17%	-1	240	345 580	P 17%	0.1	109	258 010
T 17%	-1	240	320 940	P 17%	0.1	109	262 130
T 17%	-1	220	>1 573 540	P 17%	0.1	109	200 900

Table A.8

AA6082-T6 fatigue test results, rounded to the nearest ten, of trimmed (T) and punched (P) specimens. Cutting clearances as percentage of sheet thickness.

Edge cond.	Load ratio	σ_a [MPa]	N [cycles]	Edge cond.	Load ratio	σ_a [MPa]	N [cycles]
T 7.5%	-1	170	33 990	T 7.5%	0.1	70	363 980
T 7.5%	-1	170	35 660	T 7.5%	0.1	70	>1 000 000
T 7.5%	-1	170	27 230	T 7.5%	0.1	70	975 670
T 7.5%	-1	150	48 890	T 7.5%	0.1	70	493 310
T 7.5%	-1	150	50 950	T 7.5%	0.1	70	>1 000 000
T 7.5%	-1	150	38 010	T 7.5%	0.1	60	>1 000 000
T 7.5%	-1	130	94 690	T 7.5%	0.1	60	>1 000 000
T 7.5%	-1	130	124 190	T 7.5%	0.1	60	>1 000 000
T 7.5%	-1	130	124 020	P 7.5%	0.1	60	49 420
T 7.5%	-1	110	108 970	P 7.5%	0.1	60	53 050
T 7.5%	-1	110	153 830	P 7.5%	0.1	60	53 980
T 7.5%	-1	110	449 810	P 7.5%	0.1	53	77 600
T 7.5%	0.1	120	34 110	P 7.5%	0.1	53	82 930
T 7.5%	0.1	120	33 360	P 7.5%	0.1	53	73 970
T 7.5%	0.1	120	41 400	P 7.5%	0.1	47	127 970
T 7.5%	0.1	100	81 410	P 7.5%	0.1	47	166 550
T 7.5%	0.1	100	81 270	P 7.5%	0.1	47	156 290
T 7.5%	0.1	100	65 570	P 7.5%	0.1	40	305 860
T 7.5%	0.1	80	323 800	P 7.5%	0.1	40	591 830
T 7.5%	0.1	80	225 900	P 7.5%	0.1	40	>1 000 000
T 7.5%	0.1	80	173 200				

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